

Summations Replaced with Integrals in Quantum Statistical Mechanics

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In statistical mechanics, involving quantum objects, one sometimes uses sums if a simple series sum rule exists. For example, in obtaining the Planck distribution $1/(1-\exp(-hf/T))$ one uses the sum of a geometric series. Otherwise, it seems one uses integrals, arguing that energy levels are very close together. For the Planck distribution with $1/(1-\exp(-hf/T))$ where n is 1,2,3..., one usually uses an integral, when a sum really applies. In (1), it is argued that such an integral does not yield the same result as the sum for this Planck distribution example. In particular, (1) considers f_0 as a very small number and shows explicitly that the summation depends on f_0 , while the integral does not. Given that this applies to the partition function, it carries over to all statistical quantities calculated from the partition function, as noted in (1).

Here, we consider other examples. For example, if one tries to replace the geometric series sum used to obtain the Planck distribution, in the first place, with an integral, one immediately has a degeneracy issue. A one dimensional integral over dp (p =magnitude of momentum) yields one answer, while a three-dimensional result $\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} dp$ yields another. The geometric sum, however, does not include the degeneracies of p so it is not clear why one would use a 3-dimensional integral. Even if one uses a one dimensional integral, it does not yield the same result as the geometric sum. In fact, the geometric sum depends on the value of f/T , while the integral does not - it depends on T .

Another example is the partition function for a single quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls (e.g. a Fermi gas). Again an integral is used, but it seems that using $p=p_0/a$ where a is a small number proportional to $1/L$, the length of the box and summing should yield an "a" dependent result, which the integral does not give.

Summation Versus Integral

In (1), the Planck distribution $1/(1-\exp(-hf_0/T))$ with $n=1,2,3..$ is considered. It is argued that one usually considers an integral for the partition function i.e.

$$\ln Z = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} dp \frac{1}{1-\exp(-p/T)} \quad ((1))$$

(1), however, suggests that this does not yield the same result as the summation. In particular, the summation retains the value f_0 , so in the low f_0 limit, different f_0 values yield different results. The integral result is based on the parameter T (temperature), but not on f_0 and so is completely different.

In particular, (1) calculates, for the low $x = f_0/T$ limit:

$$\text{Free energy}/(-kT) = \ln Z \approx (3.14)(3.14)/6 \cdot 1/x - .5 \ln(x/(2 \cdot 3.14)) + x/24 \quad ((2))$$

Basically, (1) provides methods of performing the sum without replacing it with an integral. Also, a low f_0 limit approach is used. Given that:

$$\text{Energy} = - d \ln Z / db \quad \text{where } b=1/kT \quad ((3))$$

One may see that taking d/b of Free energy yields:

$$E_{ave} / (kT) = (3.14)(3.14) / (6x) \cdot .5 + x/24 \quad ((4))$$

This result differs from that obtained using an integral i.e.

$$E_{ave} = \int 4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot C \cdot p \cdot dp \cdot 1 / (1 - \exp(pc/T)) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } C \text{ is a constant (not depending on } T \text{ or } f_0).$$

In (1) other quantities are calculated, but it seems sufficient to point out this differences in the summation versus integral approach. We note that a main feature is that the low f_0 limit of the summation yields a result dependent on f_0 , while the integral result does not involve f_0 , except that it tends to 0 so that n_{fo} becomes a continuous variable.

We now wish to examine some further considerations.

Planck Distribution

The question we ask is: If one may replace a summation with an integral in quantum statistics, why does one use summations at all? In particular, why does one use a summation of a geometric series in order to solve for the Planck distribution?

The Planck distribution is obtained using:

$$\text{Sum } n=1,2,3... \exp(- n f/T) = 1 / (1 - \exp(nf/T)) \quad ((6))$$

This result depends on f . If f is small and one tries to argue that the sum in ((6)) may be replaced by an integral, one immediately has a degeneracy of momentum issue. $f = |p|c$, but should one perform a one dimensional or three-dimensional integral? For a one dimensional integral one uses dp C_1 , but for a three-dimensional one, $C_2 \cdot 4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot p \cdot dp$. C_1 and C_2 are constants related to Planck's constant and π . The sum in ((6)) makes no use of momentum degeneracy in 3-space, so it is not clear why a 3-dimensional integral of dp vector should be used. This suggests a 1-dimensional integral, but this does not yield the geometric series result of ((6)) i.e.

$$\int C_1 dp \exp(-p/T) = C_1 T \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is completely different from ((6)), but because a geometric sum is known, an integral is not used, it seems, and one obtains the Planck distribution ((6)).

Partition Function of a Fermi Gas

A second example seems to be that of a Fermi gas, i.e. the partition function of a single particle in a well with infinite potential walls. The single particle energy is:

$$e = \frac{p^2}{2m} = \frac{a^2 n^2}{2m} \text{ where } a \text{ is proportional to } 1/L, L \text{ being the length of the box} \quad ((7))$$

There is no geometric series sum which may be used in this case and so it seems that a sum:

$$\text{Sum over } n \exp(- a^2 n^2 / 2mT) \quad ((8a))$$

is replaced with $C_1 \int dp \exp(-p^2/2mT)$ in 1-D nonrelativistic case $((8b))$

The problem is that the integral does not depend on “a” proportional to 1/L. One would expect results to be dependent on “a” i.e. 1/L. In particular, for $a=1/L_0$ and $a=1/(100 L_0)$, one would expect different results as each term in the sum of ((8)) maps into a smaller value for $a=1/(100 L_0)$.

Given that quantum systems usually exist in finite lengths, it may be problematic trying to consider $a \rightarrow 0$ and using an integral as this may not pertain to the physical problem, as seems to be suggested in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) points out that summations in quantum statistical mechanics, in particular a summation involving Planck’s distribution $\text{Sum over } n \frac{1}{(1 - \exp(-fn/T))}$, (with $n=1,2,3..$) when evaluated in the small f limit, does not yield the same result as an integral, namely: $\int dp \frac{1}{(1 - \exp(-pc/T))}$. (1) suggests that the mathematics exists to solve the sum and should be used. A main issue is that the sum depends on f in the low f limit, and there is a term proportional to $1/f$. The integral does not include f in its solution.

We point out that a geometric summation is used to obtain the Planck distribution in the first place, i.e. $\text{Sum over } n=1,2,3 \dots \exp(-nf/T)$. If one were to try to replace this with a one-dimension integral, one would not obtain the Planck distribution. It is critical that a summation is used, even if f is very small.

We further suggest that the partition function for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls is a sum: $\text{Sum over } n=1,2,3 \dots \exp(- a^2 n^2 / 2mT)$ where a is proportional to $1/L$, the length of the one dimensional box. A summation should yield a result related to “a”, but converting the sum to an integral, which is usually done, does not. Thus, there seems to be a disconnect between using summations and integrals in quantum statistics, at least in certain circumstances, as argued in (1).

References

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